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Research Article

**ELEUSINE INDICA: MINERAL ANALYSIS AND ANTI-
CONVULSANT POTENTIAL IN NMRI MICE****Andouormwine Abel SOMÉ¹, Stanislas SAWADOGO*¹, Anankpètinan Prosper
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Faso³Banfora Polytechnic University Center (CUP/B), Burkina Faso.**Abstract:**

This study evaluated the anticonvulsant potential of the aqueous extract of Eleusine indica and explored the link between its biological activity and its unique mineral composition. Animal groups fasted for 12 hours were treated preventively with diazepam or AEEi one hour before administration of isoniazid (convulsant). The results obtained showed that a dose of 600 mg/kg of Eleusine indica aqueous extract (AEEi) significantly increased the latency period before the onset of seizures and the survival time of the animals. It also significantly reduced the mortality rate from 100% to 40% in the case of an isoniazid-induced epileptic seizure in NMRI mice. Mineral analysis revealed a composition dominated by potassium (106.52 mg/g) and magnesium (13.73 mg/g), with notable levels of copper, zinc, and selenium. The anticonvulsant action of AEEi would therefore involve complex mechanisms involving the modulation of GABA and NMDA receptors as well as the ionic inhibition of pro-oxidative reactions induced by epileptic seizures.

Keywords: *Eleusine indica, Anticonvulsant Activity, Mineral signature, GABAergic System, Oxidative*

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1. INTRODUCTION :

Epilepsy and seizure disorders are conditions that affect more than 50 million people worldwide [1, 2]. Low-income regions with limited access to conventional anti-epileptic drugs are the most affected, accounting for nearly 80% of cases [3, 4]. Although conventional treatments exist, it should be noted that existing anti-epileptic drugs often have serious side effects, including cognitive impairment [5,6] and cases of hepatotoxicity [7,8]. Research into medicinal plants therefore offers an accessible and safer alternative for the management of these conditions. *Eleusine indica* (Poaceae) is a traditional medicinal plant whose antioxidant, hepatoprotective, and nephroprotective properties have already been demonstrated by numerous researchers [9,10]. The beneficial effects of *E. indica* on cognitive function were also demonstrated by Etebong et al. in 2016 [11]. However, its mineral composition and potential anticonvulsant properties remain to be explored. In view of all the properties previously studied, we therefore hypothesize that the aqueous extract of *Eleusine indica* (AEEi) exhibits significant anticonvulsant activity in NMRI mice, thanks to its content of bioactive minerals that modulate neuronal excitability. The overall objective of this study was to evaluate the mineral composition of the aqueous extract of *Eleusine indica* and its anticonvulsant effects in vivo in NMRI mice.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1. Sample collection and plant extraction

E. indica leaves were collected in Bobo-Dioulasso, located in the western part of Burkina Faso. The leaves were air-dried at room temperature and ground into a fine powder. The resulting powder was macerated in distilled water at room temperature for 48 hours. The macerate was then filtered, and the filtrate was oven-dried at 40°C. The resulting dry extract was stored at -4°C in a moisture-free environment.[12].

2.2 Extract metal content analysis

For mineral analysis, the AFNOR NF methods T90-119 and EN 1483 were used. A total amount of 0.25 g of dry extract was introduced into 50 mL of pure water, and the pH was adjusted to 2.5 using a 1M nitric acid solution. The mixture was mechanically stirred for 18 hours to ensure complete dissolution

and to obtain a well-homogenized solution. The resulting solution was analyzed by ICP-OES to quantify the metal content. For the analysis of calcium, magnesium, potassium, and sodium, 0.25 g of extract was dissolved in 50 mL of pure water (pH=6.95 at 25°C). Calcium and magnesium were determined by EDTA titration. Potassium and sodium were quantified using selective electrodes. [13].

2.3 Anticonvulsant Activity Determination of the Anticonvulsant Activity of the Extract

For this study, 30 male NMRI mice weighing between 20 and 30g were used. They were divided into five groups of five animals each. Before the experimental procedure began, the animals were first submitted to a 12-hour non-hydric fast. Thus, the first group (Group 1), considered as the normal control group, and the second Group (positive control) received distilled water 10 mL/kg. The Group 3 received diazepam (10mg/kg), while Groups 4 and 5 received the aqueous extract of *E. indica* at respective doses of 50 and 600 mg/kg of body weight. One hour later, all groups except Group 1 were additionally administered isoniazid (INH) at a dose of 300 mg/kg of body weight 1 hour before the start of the experiment. All substance administrations in this study were performed orally. One hour after the administration of isoniazid, each mouse was placed individually in a transparent cage and filmed for 60 minutes. The latency time before the onset of convulsions was measured for each animal, and the mortality rate was recorded in each group. [14].

3. RESULTS:

3.1. Effects of AEEi on epileptic seizure latency time following animal pretreatment with a convulsant agent

The anticonvulsant activity of the extract was measured by its effect on the latency time preceding the onset of the first convulsions. A prolongation of this delay indicates an inhibitory effect on the process leading to epileptic seizure establishment. Pretreatment of animals with the 600 mg/kg dose of the extract significantly prolonged the latency time (Figure 1) before the onset of convulsions, supporting the hypothesis of a dose-dependent anticonvulsant effect.

Figure 1: Effect of *Eleusine indica* pretreatment on seizure onset latency

The data represent the mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) for $n=6-8$ animals per group. Statistical significance was determined by analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's post-hoc test. The latency time is defined as the time elapsed between the injection of INH and the onset of the first tonic-clonic convulsion..). ** $p<0.01$ significant difference compared to INH

3.2. Preventive effects of *Eleusine indica* on mortality in NMRI mice during INH-induced convulsions

The administration of INH caused 100% mortality in the negative control group. treatment with diazepam completely prevented mortality (0%). Treatment with the low dose of extract (50 mg/kg) did not show a significant protective effect (100% mortality), whereas the high dose (600 mg/kg) significantly reduced the mortality rate to 40%.

Table 1: Protective effects of *E. indica* on INH-induced mortality

GROUPS	DOSE	MORTALITY	MORTALITY (%)	P-VALUE VS INE
H2O Control	10ml/kg	0/5	00	$p<0.001$
DZP	10(mg/kg) per os	0 /5	00	$p<0.001$
<i>E. INDICA</i>	50(mg/kg) per os	5/5	100	$p>0.05$
<i>E. INDICA</i>	600(mg/kg) per os	2/5	40	$p<0.001$
<i>Isoniazid control</i>	300 (mg/kg) per os	5/5	100	

The administration of INH provoked 100% mortality in the negative control group (distilled H₂O). Pretreatment with diazepam) completely prevented mortality (0%). Pretreatment with the low dose of extract (50 mg/kg) did not show a significant protective effect (100% mortality), whereas the high dose (600 mg/kg) significantly reduced the mortality rate to 40%, i.e., 2 deaths out of 5 animals.

3.3. Effect of the aqueous extract of *Eleusine indica* (AEEi) on the survival of NMRI mice subjected to isoniazid (INH)-induced convulsions

The anticonvulsant activity of the extract was evaluated using the isoniazid (INH)-induced convulsion model. INH is an inhibitor of GABA synthesis. Animal survival was monitored kinetically over a 60-minute period. The Kaplan-Meier plot (Figure 2) shows that pretreatment with the high dose of extract (600 mg/kg) conferred a significant protective effect, delaying the onset of mortality in a manner comparable to the reference standard, diazepam. The low dose (50 mg/kg) showed a trend towards protection without being as effective (figure 2).

Figure 2: Kaplan-Meier survival plot

Groups were pretreated orally with distilled water (H_2O dist, negative control), diazepam (Diazepam, 10 mg/kg, positive control), or two doses of the extract (50 and 600 mg/kg). Lethal convulsion was induced by administration of a 300 mg/kg dose of INH ($n=5$ per group). *** $p<0.001$ significant difference compared to INH

3.4. Mineral content of AEEi

Table 2: Macro-elements content in the aqueous extract of *Eleusine indica*

	Valeurs	SEM	method
Ca (mg/g)	19,17	0,21	NF EN ISO 7980
Na (mg/g)	12,05	0,021	NF EN ISO 11885
K (mg/g)	106,52	0,021	NF EN ISO 11885
Mg (mg/g)	13,73	0,21	NF EN ISO 7980

Mineral characterization of the aqueous extract revealed a composition dominated by cations essential for maintaining electrolyte and neuronal homeostasis. The results, presented in Table 1, show a particularly marked abundance of potassium. Values represent the mean of n measurements; SEM: standard error of the mean.

Table 3: Trace Elements

	Valeurs	SEM	method
Zn (mg/g)	0,113	0,002	AFNOR T90-112
V (μ g/g)	<2	2	AFNOR T90-119
Se (μ g/g)	8	2	AFNOR T90-119
Cr (μ g/g)	<2	2	AFNOR T90-119
Cu (μ g/g)	65	2	NF AO6-755
Fe (μ g/g)	<2	2	AFNOR NF T90-112

Analysis of trace elements, which are crucial for their role as enzymatic cofactors and modulators of neuronal activity, revealed notable levels of copper and selenium, while other elements were present below the method's detection threshold (Table 2). Values represent the mean of n measurements; SEM: standard error of the mean; <2: value below the method's detection limit; Dosage methods: AFNOR standards.

4.DISCUSSION:

In this study, we evaluated the anticonvulsant potential of *Eleusine indica* aqueous extract and the correlation between this response and its mineral signature. A detailed analysis of behavioral and survival parameters reveals that AEEi has both preventive and protective effects against seizures and INH toxicity in mice. Thus, our study demonstrated that a dose of 600 mg/kg of extract significantly prolongs the latency period before the

onset of the first seizure compared to the control group treated with INH exclusively. Indeed, INH acts by inhibiting pyridoxine phosphokinase, the enzyme responsible for activating vitamin B6. This vitamin is essential for the synthesis of the neurotransmitter GABA. Consequently, the inhibition of pyridoxine phosphokinase by INH induces a depletion of the active form of vitamin B6. The resulting decrease in GABA synthesis leads to neuronal hyperexcitability and seizures. The

increase in latency time before seizures suggests that the extract not only slows down the onset of seizures, but also interferes with the upstream epileptogenic process. In fact, two non-exclusive mechanisms could explain the effect of our extract: these include the potentiation of residual GABA activity at the postsynaptic level, via allosteric modulation of GABA receptors by magnesium and zinc present in the extract, and a stabilizing action on the neuronal membrane induced by its potassium content, which could hyperpolarize the membrane and increase the threshold for triggering paroxysmal discharges [15,16,17,18,19,20]. The mortality data and Kaplan-Meier survival graph indicate dose-dependent protective and anticonvulsant activity. Indeed, the 50 mg/kg dose of extract proved inefficient, with 100% mortality and a survival profile similar to that of INH, while the 600 mg/kg dose significantly reduced mortality from 100% to 40% ($p < 0.001$). Furthermore, the survival profile of the group treated with 600 mg/kg AEEi was between that of diazepam, which provides complete protection, and that of INH, which induces rapid mortality. This result shows that the extract not only reduces the number of deaths but also retards the onset of death in unprotected animals. This result clearly demonstrates that our extract (at 600mg/kg) increases the animal's resistance to the convulsive effect of INH by reducing the severity of epileptic seizures. This results in both an increase in animal survival and a delay in the onset of death in unprotected animals. The mineralogical analysis of AEEi reveals a profile dominated by potassium (K^+ , 106.52 mg/g), followed by calcium (Ca^{2+} , 19.17 mg/g), magnesium (Mg^{2+} , 13.73 mg/g), and sodium (Na^+ , 12.05 mg/g). Among the trace elements, we noted a relative abundance of copper (Cu, 65 μ g/g) and selenium (Se, 8 μ g/g), while zinc (Zn, 0.113 mg/g) is present in moderate proportions. As for vanadium (V), chromium (Cr), and iron (Fe), their levels are below the detection limits ($< 2 \mu$ g/g) of our analysis method. Under physiological conditions, the plasma concentration of K^+ and calcium is actively regulated in the kidney through the excretion of excess ions. However, a moderate extracellular residual concentration of K^+ that is slightly above normal could promote neuronal repolarization and stabilization of the membrane potential, thereby limiting hypersynchronous discharges. On the other hand, excessive extracellular K^+ concentrations (in cases of renal impairment) can open voltage-dependent calcium channels, leading to nervous system dysfunction [21, 22]. This effect is most likely potentiated by the concomitant presence of magnesium at a significant concentration (13.73 mg/g). Mg^{2+} is known as a natural antagonist of NMDA receptors and a calcium channel blocker [20,15]. Its action helps to inhibit the excitability of neurons in the central nervous system. As for Zn^{2+} , it is known as an allosteric

modulator of GABA and NMDA receptors. Although its content is low, it remains physiologically active. Its action on these receptors leads to an increase in neuronal inhibition [16]. Our extract also demonstrated a significant copper and selenium content. Copper is known as a cofactor of copper/zinc superoxide dismutase as long as the pro-oxidant level is not reached. This suggests that our extract may contribute to the body's defense against oxidative stress induced by epileptic seizures [23,24]. Selenium, for its part, is thought to be involved in the detoxification of lipid peroxides generated during epileptic seizures through interaction with glutathione peroxidase. [25,26]. The considerable absence of iron is a real advantage insofar as it eliminates the potential risk of catalyzing pro-oxidative reactions that could neutralize the beneficial effects of our extract [26,27]. Furthermore, ions with levels below the detection limits (iron, vanadium, and chromium) cannot contribute significantly to the biological activity of our extract. The anticonvulsant and protective activity of our extract in NMRI mice appears to result from a complex mechanism involving the modulation of GABA and NMDA receptors as well as the ionic inhibition of pro-oxidant reactions induced by epileptic seizures.

CONCLUSION :

At the end of this study, we can confirm that AEEi has anticonvulsant properties, which are reflected in an increase in the latency period before convulsions, a reduction in mortality, and an increase in survival time in animals. These beneficial effects of our extract in mice appear to be mainly due to its high content of bioactive minerals, particularly magnesium, selenium, potassium, and zinc-copper. The anticonvulsant action would therefore involve complex mechanisms involving the modulation of GABA and NMDA receptors as well as the ionic inhibition of pro-oxidative reactions induced by epileptic seizures.

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